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Human Minds, Machine Hands: Rethinking Authorship in The Age of Generative AI

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Abstract

The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in creative processes and its implications for copyright law have become central issues in contemporary legal scholarship. Generative AI challenges the traditional understanding of creativity and originality in art. Copyright law in most jurisdictions is grounded in anthropocentric theories that place the human creator at its core, viewing copyright primarily as a means to incentivise human creativity. If this human-centred approach continues to prevail, moral rights will remain the main focus of copyright protection. However, this position risks conflicting with current technological and economic developments, potentially leading to a situation where truly original and innovative works produced by intelligent machines fall into the public domain. Such an outcome could discourage investment in and use of generative AI technologies. To address this issue, the present study adopts a utilitarian theory, which conceives copyright as an instrument to promote the creation of works that enrich society. From this viewpoint, extending copyright protection to AI-generated works could motivate human stakeholders—developers, users, and owners—to further develop and employ these technologies. The paper analyses the advantages and drawbacks of recognising each of these stakeholders as potential authors and ultimately argues for attributing copyright ownership to the AI system's owner through statutory provisions that permit contractual allocation between parties. The

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proposed framework seeks to resolve doctrinal uncertainties surrounding AI authorship and provide a foundation for future research.

Keywords: Generative AI, Copyright Law, Authorship, Originality, Utilitarian Theory.

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1. Introduction

For centuries, it was widely believed that the creation of literary and artistic works was a uniquely human endeavour. However, the emergence of artificial intelligence has given rise to algorithmic systems capable of engaging in cultural creativity, challenging this long-held assumption (Yanisky-Ravid, 2017, p.662; Bridy, 2016, p.397; Ralston, 2005, p.283). The term *generative art*—a concept originating in the creative industries rather than in legal discourse—generally refers to artistic works produced entirely or partially through the use of autonomous systems, that is, systems designed to execute creative tasks independently (Abbott and Rothman, 2023, p.1148). In the 1960s and 1970s, the field of generative art began to attract broader recognition, particularly through the work of abstract artist Harold Cohen, who created *AARON*—a computer program designed to produce drawings and, in later stages, paintings with only limited human input (Cohen, 2016, pp.63-64). In contemporary times, public access to text-to-image generation models such as *DALL·E 2*, *Midjourney*, and *Firefly* has further transformed artistic production. By entering a simple text prompt, users can instruct the AI to generate an image that visually represents the provided description. This technique has sparked debate about the level of human creativity required to claim authorship (Abbott and Rothman, 2023, p.1150). Similar to a human artist who refines their style through years of study and imitation, generative AI models develop their capacity for originality by being trained on vast datasets of textual and visual material. For instance, *DALL·E 2* was trained on more than 650 million pairs of images and textual descriptions (Ramesh et al., 2022, p.23). Some AI systems even create artworks independently by integrating both linguistic and visual generation processes. A notable example is *Botto*, an AI artist that autonomously produces around 350 artworks each week without any direct human input. It formulates its own text prompts, titles, and descriptions, while the limited human role is confined to curating and moderating its outputs to prevent the use of inappropriate or biased material (Abbott and Rothman, 2023, p.1153). Beyond the visual arts, artificial intelligence has expanded into numerous creative domains, including journalism, website content creation, poetry, and literature. Moreover, AI technology is increasingly employed in the field of music composition. For example, the *Artificial Intelligence Virtual Artist* (AIVA) system has been officially acknowledged by

SACEM—a French non-profit organisation responsible for managing artists’ rights—as a classical music composer that autonomously generates musical works used in film, advertising, and video game soundtracks (Abbott and Rothman, 2023, pp.1154-1155).

The increasing incorporation of artificial intelligence (AI) systems into artistic creation has introduced intricate legal questions that demand a sophisticated analysis of the relationship between copyright principles and technological advancement. A key concern—forming the central inquiry of this study—relates to determining who should be regarded as the “author” of works generated by AI. Historically, the entire framework of copyright and intellectual property law has been built upon the notion of human authorship. However, the emergence of AI and its expanding role as a creative collaborator has profoundly disrupted this long-established legal paradigm. As artificial intelligence systems become increasingly involved in the creation of literary, musical, and visual works, the question of who should be legally acknowledged as the author has emerged as a matter of considerable debate among legislators, policymakers, and courts. Employing both analytical and comparative methods, this article explores the contemporary framework of copyright law and judicial practice across multiple jurisdictions, namely the United States, the United Kingdom, the European Union, and China. These legal systems have been chosen for their active engagement in disputes and policy discussions surrounding the authorship of AI-generated creations, which underscores the practical significance of this inquiry. The study draws upon doctrinal analysis, academic commentary, and case law to present a holistic understanding of the shifting legal notions of authorship in the era of artificial intelligence.

This paper explores whether creations produced by artificial intelligence can meet the originality threshold required for copyright protection and, if they do, how authorship should be properly ascribed. It evaluates several possible claimants to authorship—the programmer, the end user, the owner of the system, and even the AI itself—considering the strengths and shortcomings of each position. Through an examination of relevant jurisprudence and theoretical analyses, the article seeks to enrich the current scholarly and legal discussion on AI authorship and to advance a reasoned perspective on how authorship rights ought to be allocated within the framework of contemporary copyright doctrine.

2. The Human Author Paradigm in Common Law and Civil Law Systems

In common law jurisdictions such as the United States, the United Kingdom, Ireland, Malta, and New Zealand, an ongoing debate concerns the potential recognition of non-human entities as authors within copyright law. These legal systems are traditionally grounded in a utilitarian rationale, seeking to incentivise creative production while ensuring public access to cultural goods. Because this framework places comparatively less emphasis on the personality of the creator, it may, at least at a theoretical level, appear open to the possibility of recognising authorship by artificial or non-human agents. Judicial practice in the United States, however, reflects a markedly restrictive approach to this question, firmly anchoring copyright protection in human creative activity. The U.S. Copyright Act of 1976 explicitly highlights the requirement of human authorship. In line with this, the U.S. Copyright Office has long maintained the view that copyright subsists only in works produced by human beings

(Compendium of US Copyright Office Practices, 2021, art. 306, ch. 300). In its interpretation of the Copyright Act, the U.S. Supreme Court has emphasised that copyright protection applies exclusively to works produced by human creators. This interpretation restricts the scope of copyright to those creations that embody human intellectual input. A notable example is the case of *Burrow-Giles Lithographic Co. v. Sarony*, in which the Court defined an author as the “originator” or “maker” of a work, explicitly acknowledging that photographs can represent the original intellectual expression of their creator. The ruling in *Feist Publications, Inc. v. Rural Telephone Service Company, Inc.* clarified that a work is eligible for copyright protection only if it is original to its creator and demonstrates a sufficient level of creativity and personal contribution. The Office’s guidelines further clarify that it “will not register works produced by a machine or mere mechanical process that operates randomly or automatically without any creative input or intervention from a human author” (Compendium of US Copyright Office Practices, 2021, art.313.2). This highlights that, under U.S. law, copyright protection requires the presence of human creativity, even in works produced with the aid of technological tools (Senftleben and Buijtelaar, 2020, p. 4).

Within the European Union, the concept of authorship is intrinsically tied to the requirement of originality. In *Infopaq International v. Danske Dagblades Forening*, the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) articulated a general standard of originality applicable to all “literary and artistic” works, defining it as “the author’s own intellectual creation.” In further developing this notion, the Court emphasised that a work must embody the exercise of “free and creative choices” (*Football Dataco Ltd and Ors v. Yahoo! UK Ltd and Ors*, para. 38). and reflect the author’s “personal touch” (*Eva-Maria Painer v. Standardd VerlagsGmbH and Ors*, para. 92). Although the CJEU has not expressly stated that copyright protection under the EU *acquis* is limited to human authors, its repeated emphasis on elements such as “personal touch” and “personality” (*Cofemel–Sociedade de Vestua’rio SA v. G-Star Raw CV*, para. 30)—attributes inherently associated with human beings—strongly indicates that originality is understood as requiring a human dimension. This anthropocentric approach reflects the deep influence of the European tradition of author’s rights (*droit d’auteur*), which places the author’s individuality at the core of protection (Xiao, 2023, pp.10-11).

Section 178 of the UK Copyright, Designs and Patents Act 1988 (CDPA) represents one of the earliest statutory attempts to address works produced by computers when no identifiable human author can be determined, providing under Section 9(3) that, for literary, dramatic, musical, or artistic works generated by a computer, the author is considered to be the individual who made the arrangements necessary for the work’s creation. By this formulation, authorship is attributed not to the machine itself, but to the individual who has made the essential arrangements leading to the work’s production. This approach demonstrates that, even in the age of advanced technologies, human originality continues to play a decisive role in the recognition of copyrightable works so long as AI systems lack consciousness or autonomous creative capacity (Jaramillo, 2024, p.40).

3. Justifying Copyright for AI-Generated Works: From Human Labour to Societal Benefit

Copyright law has traditionally been justified through several principal theories, reflecting different perspectives on the role of human creativity and societal benefit, including labour-based and personality theories, as well as the economic and utilitarian theory (Longan, 2023).

3.1. Locke's Labour Theory and Hegelian Personality Theory

Appropriation theories hold that a person gains legitimate rights over an idea or creative process by being the first to claim or utilise it. These theories place emphasis on the author's creative contribution, adopting a creator-centric perspective that justifies ownership rights through the individual's labour or through the realisation of the self in the creative act (Longan, 2023, pp.781-782). Within this framework, *John Locke's labour theory* has been particularly influential. Locke argued that individuals acquire property rights over the products of their labour. If treated as a labourer in the Lockean sense, AI could be considered the owner of its creations. Yet such an interpretation is problematic: Locke's theory is inherently centred on human beings, emphasising that individuals possess natural rights over the products of their own labour; because artificial intelligence is not a person, it cannot hold these rights (du Bois, 2018, p.8). The second appropriation theory, often referred to as the *Hegelian personality theory*, offers little support for extending copyright protection to works generated by AI. According to this perspective, creative works are intimately connected to the creator's sense of self and personal development. Hegel regarded intellectual property as a safeguard for the author's self-expression and dignity. Within this framework, copyright law is justified primarily as a means of protecting the creator's moral rights (du Bois, 2018, pp.24-25). Since AI systems do not engage in creative activity as a form of self-expression and lack both consciousness and legal personality, they cannot be considered bearers of moral rights. By contrast, the human creators or users of AI remain entitled to such protection, as their dignity and self-expression are implicated in the process. Consequently, according to the personality theory, copyright protection applies solely to the humans who create or operate an AI system, rather than to the system itself.

3.2. Economic and Utilitarian Theories

The question of granting copyright to AI-generated works can also be examined from economic and utilitarian perspectives, foundational approaches in intellectual property law, which view copyright primarily as a tool to encourage the production of works that benefit society (Padmanabhan and Wadsworth, 2024, p.159). Granting copyright to such works could, at least in principle, stimulate further investment in AI technologies and encourage the dissemination of socially useful creations, thereby aligning with the objectives of copyright law (Abbott and Rothman, 2023, p. 1144). According to the *economic theory*, copyright achieves its purpose by providing economic incentives that motivate the creation of new works. When applied to artificial intelligence, however, this rationale encounters a conceptual difficulty, as AI systems themselves lack the capacity to perceive or respond to financial

incentives. Nevertheless, the economic approach does not require that such incentives be directed at the machine itself. Rather, the protection of AI-generated works may operate indirectly by motivating the human stakeholders behind these systems—developers, designers, and users—to continue refining the technology and producing creative outputs.

This incentive-based logic closely aligns with *utilitarian theory*, which evaluates legal rules according to their capacity to maximise overall social welfare while minimising collective harm. In the copyright context, utilitarian reasoning places particular emphasis on the interests of the broader public, given that the number of users and consumers of creative works typically exceeds that of their creators. From this perspective, expansive public access to creative outputs may appear desirable. Nevertheless, utilitarian theory does not support unrestricted freedom of use where such freedom would undermine the conditions necessary for continued creative production. The absence of copyright protection, even for AI-generated works, risks diminishing incentives for those who develop and deploy such technologies, potentially leading to a reduction in both the quantity and diversity of creative outputs. A decline in creative activity would, in turn, negatively affect overall societal welfare. Utilitarian reasoning therefore favours neither absolute exclusivity nor complete openness, but rather a calibrated system of protection that is sufficient to stimulate creative activity without unduly restricting public access to cultural goods (Longan, 2023, pp.798-801).

Consistent with this view, *Thambaiya, Kariyawasam and Talagala* observe that society as a whole may benefit from an increased availability of works, particularly given that human judgment remains indispensable at every stage of the creative process, from curating datasets to shaping and evaluating outputs. At the same time, they caution that the absence of meaningful rewards for those who develop or employ AI systems to generate creative content may undermine incentives to contribute, thereby reducing the dissemination of works that might otherwise possess significant social value (Thambaiya, Kariyawasam and Talagala, 2025, pp.18-19).

3.3. Summary

This article adopts that copyright should not be interpreted exclusively from the perspective of the human author, nor should the criteria of originality and creativity be confined solely to the individual who produces the work. Contemporary technological developments, particularly the emergence of artificial intelligence systems in the artistic domain, demand a broader and more flexible understanding of copyright law. Contemporary AI systems are capable of generating outputs that display a degree of originality and creative complexity comparable to that of human-made works. Where such outputs possess commercial relevance, artistic merit, or cultural value, and contribute meaningfully to innovation and social enrichment, a complete exclusion from copyright protection becomes increasingly difficult to justify. From this perspective, it may be argued that copyright law should place greater emphasis on the characteristics of the work itself, rather than relying exclusively on a rigid conception of authorship tied to the personal qualities of a natural person.

This approach, however, appears at first glance to stand in tension with the prevailing paradigms of Continental European copyright systems, which have traditionally been grounded in an author-centred and personality-based conception of copyright. Yet this tension does not necessarily preclude accommodation. Even within civil law jurisdictions, it is widely recognised that creative works do not emerge in isolation but are often the result of complex production processes involving multiple forms of human input. In the context of AI-generated works, it is evident that even the most autonomous systems remain dependent on human involvement, whether through the design of algorithms, the selection and curation of training data, or the formulation of prompts and evaluative choices. A solution compatible with the foundations of Continental European copyright law therefore lies not in recognising AI systems as authors, but in adopting a functional interpretation of human authorship. Under such an approach, authorship would be attributed to the human actor who exercises a decisive creative influence/control over the production of the work, even where that influence is mediated through advanced technological systems. This allows the personalist structure of copyright law to be preserved, while avoiding the categorical exclusion of AI-generated works from protection.

Accordingly, while copyright must continue to be reserved for human subjects rather than artificial systems, AI-generated works should not be denied protection solely on the basis of the means through which they are produced. The remaining challenge—one that will be addressed in the following section—lies in determining which human participants in the AI-assisted creative process merit recognition as authors or rights-holders. This issue remains complex and unresolved, but it is clear that a civil-law solution must balance fidelity to the concept of authorship with the practical realities of contemporary creative production.

4. Programmer/Developer as an Author of the AI – Generated Works

4.1. The Programmer as the Creative Mind Behind AI Systems

Programmers are the individuals who design and construct the software underlying artificial intelligence systems. The argument supporting the attribution of authorship to developers rests on several key points. Firstly, programming demands significant intellectual engagement, which supports the recognition of programmers as the authors of their creations and the consequent entitlement to copyright protection. Viewed in this light, outputs generated by AI or robotic systems can be considered expressions of the programmer’s original creative vision, as they are produced within the structured parameters set by the developer. This framework is possible because developers generally determine the system’s operational boundaries, thereby guiding both user interactions and the system’s autonomous functions (Bonadio and McDonagh, 2020, p.5). It is the programmer who determines whether the algorithm will incorporate elements of creativity, randomness, or rule-breaking behaviour—each of these features originates from intentional human design. Moreover, the programmer effectively “animates” the AI’s functioning. The creative capacity attributed to the algorithm exists solely because of the programmer’s choices in structuring, refining, and adjusting its parameters (Samuelson, 1986, pp.1205-1209). In reality, an algorithm possesses no inherent ability to generate output beyond the potential endowed by its creator. It serves as an extension

of human creativity rather than an autonomous source of innovation. Even when an algorithm produces seemingly original or inventive outcomes, such results are ultimately a reflection of the human intellect embedded within its design and programming (Thi, 2023, p.306). A notable illustration of this approach can be found in the recent Chinese case *Tencent v Shanghai Yingxun Technology Co. Ltd*, where the court recognised that the software developer’s creative input into an AI-generated work was sufficient to establish ownership. The case involved an article produced by Tencent’s AI, Dreamwriter, which automatically collected, analysed, and verified data before drafting and publishing the content. The defendant contended that the article lacked human creativity and therefore could not be protected under copyright law. The court disagreed, emphasising that human originality was present in the process: although Dreamwriter generated the article automatically, the system operated according to the developer’s deliberate creative decisions, such as selecting and organising data, setting parameters for the writing process, designing templates, structuring the data collection, and training the verification algorithms (Matulionyte and Lee, 2022, pp.17-18).

Another key argument supporting the attribution of copyright to developers rests on the need to provide incentives for creation. Programmers devote considerable intellectual and physical effort to constructing functional AI systems, investing significant time and labour in developing generative algorithms. The logic of this approach emphasises that offering financial rewards through copyright protection motivates programmers to continue developing innovative systems, thereby fostering societal progress (Thongmeensuk, 2024, p.86).

4.2. The Incompatibility of Programmer Authorship with Copyright Principles

Some scholars have raised objections to granting copyright in AI-generated works to programmers, pointing to several key considerations. They argue that attributing authorship is only justifiable where the AI system leaves little or no scope for users to exercise creative judgment. From this perspective, developers must structure the AI in a way that limits the variability and unpredictability of its generated outputs (Senftleben and Buijtelaar, 2020, p.10). When the results produced by an AI system are highly unpredictable, causing the model to function as an entirely autonomous system, it is unlikely that copyright would extend to the programmer. In these cases, the role of the AI developer resembles that of an art instructor supervising the creative efforts of their students (Senftleben and Buijtelaar, 2020, pp.6-7). A clear example of this reasoning can be found in the case of ChatGPT. The system is not designed to produce a predetermined result but to generate a wide range of unpredictable outputs based on the specific instructions provided by users, who are the primary agents shaping the final content. Consequently, it would be unrealistic to regard OpenAI as supervising or exercising creative control over each individual output produced by ChatGPT. A more accurate characterisation would be to view OpenAI as the provider of an extensive repository of raw materials that the model can utilise in generating responses, while users act as the instructors who guide and limit the model’s use of these materials in accordance with their intentions. The originality of ChatGPT’s outputs arises from the prompts formulated by users rather than from the datasets on which the model was trained. Therefore, identifying programmers of generative AI systems as the authors of AI-generated works—outputs they are

likely unaware of—does not constitute a coherent or defensible position within the framework of copyright law (Söğüt, 2024, p.51).

Pamela Samuelson argues that although AI designers make substantial intellectual contributions to the development of artificial intelligence systems, these contributions are already safeguarded under copyright law as part of the designer's software work. Extending copyright protection to include the AI-generated content (AIGC) produced by that software would, therefore, amount to a form of duplicate protection (Samuelson, 1986, p.1207). Such an approach would enable AI designers to benefit twice from the same intellectual achievement, leading to an inequitable distribution of rights and rewards.

4.3. Summary

Despite the doctrinal arguments and certain judicial precedents supporting the attribution of authorship to programmers of AI systems, this article endorses the counter-view that developers should not be recognised as authors of AI-generated works. The main reason for this position lies in the fundamental incompatibility of such attribution with the core principles of copyright law.

As previously discussed, authorship requires a demonstrable intellectual and creative connection between the author and the work. The work must embody the personal imprint of its creator, reflecting individual choices and expressive effort. This essential bond can indeed be observed between the programmer and the AI system itself. When developing the algorithm, the programmer conceives an idea of how the system should function, defines its operational logic, determines its capacities and limitations, and invests in substantial knowledge, skill, and labour to bring the system into existence. Hence, the AI system as software may justifiably be regarded as the programmer's creative work, meriting copyright protection. However, this connection does not extend to the outputs subsequently generated by that system. For instance, consider a developer who designs an algorithm capable of producing realistic or cartoon-style images in response to text prompts. While there exists a direct creative link between the developer and the software that enables such image generation, no such link can be established between the developer and the specific images later produced by the AI. The programmer neither formulates the textual prompts, nor determines the visual parameters such as style, colour palette, or composition. These creative choices belong to the user who interacts with the AI, defines the input parameters, and shapes the conceptual direction of the resulting image. This distinction may be illustrated by analogy: a guitar manufacturer cannot claim authorship over a musical composition merely because the instrument they created was used by a musician to produce it. Similarly, the programmer of an AI system cannot claim authorship over the works created through the user's interaction with that system. Unless the programmer and the user are one and the same, or the programmer has intentionally limited the user's contribution to a purely mechanical task—such as executing a simple command—the programmer's involvement remains too detached from the work's ultimate creative expression.

Once authorship is excluded at the level of the AI system and its developer, the analysis necessarily shifts to the role of the user who engages with the system in the creative process. Nevertheless, it cannot be assumed that every form of user interaction with an AI system amounts to a sufficient personal contribution for the purposes of copyright law. Mere directives—such as instructing the system to “proceed in a certain manner” or to “follow predefined instructions”—may fall short of establishing the kind of creative input required for authorship. A useful parallel may be drawn to the situation in which an individual merely advises a painter to depict a landscape in a particular way: such guidance alone would not ordinarily justify a claim to authorship in the resulting work. By contrast, where the user exercises substantive creative control over the expressive elements of the output—by formulating prompts that reflect individual aesthetic choices, iteratively refining inputs, and determining the final form and selection of the result, the user’s contribution may embody the requisite personal imprint. In such cases, the user does not merely trigger a technical process but actively shapes the creative outcome through the AI system as a tool. It is only under these conditions that the user may be regarded as contributing the “personal touch” necessary for copyright protection. The question of when this threshold is met, and how such creative control should be assessed in practice, will be examined in greater detail in the following section.

5. User as an Author of the AI – Generated Works

5.1. Legal and Practical Arguments for User Authorship

The concept of a user refers to an individual who operates a computer program, either through ownership obtained by purchase or by virtue of a valid usage license. Although artificial intelligence systems can produce works autonomously, the user often plays an essential part in steering the creative process and refining the final result to meet a specific vision. This participation may involve formulating prompts, setting parameters, or offering instructions and feedback to the system. Such engagement surpasses a simple mechanical action; it requires iterative experimentation and the modification of multiple prompts until the desired outcome is achieved, thereby evidencing a degree of intellectual effort in the creation process (Thambaiya, Kariyawasam and Talagala, 2025, pp.16-17). Accordingly, when the user’s involvement in shaping the work is substantial, copyright ownership may appropriately be attributed to that user. Conversely, in instances where the work is generated with minimal user input—such as simply initiating a basic command (Perry and Margoni, 2010, p.627)—the user’s claim to authorship cannot be sustained. If the user’s input does not rise to the level of creative contribution, any ownership rights over the resulting work should therefore be denied (Pearlman, 2017, p.27). Given that the human user is the one who fixes the computer-generated work in a tangible form and can enhance the raw output by adding creative and commercial value, it appears reasonable to regard the user of a generative system as the most suitable candidate for copyright protection (Samuelson, 1986, p.1204). A notable example supporting this view can be found in the recent case *Li v. Liu*. In this decision, the Beijing Internet Court recognised that the AI-generated image in question qualified for copyright protection under Chinese Copyright Law. The court emphasised that the plaintiff’s creative input—such as designing the character, determining its presentation style, and configuring various image elements through prompts and parameter settings—demonstrated a process of

selection and arrangement reflecting personal judgment. Furthermore, after obtaining the initial image, the plaintiff continued to refine it by providing additional prompts, modifying parameters, and making iterative adjustments until achieving the final version. This process of ongoing revision and enhancement was deemed to manifest the plaintiff's aesthetic discernment and individual creative effort (Yu, 2025, p.781).

Acknowledging users as authors and granting them relevant rights would incentivise them to adopt and employ computer programs to create new works, placing them in the strongest position to commercialise and disseminate the resulting outputs. This dynamic could, in turn, benefit programmers, as users' increased interest in purchasing and employing these programs would enhance the software's overall market value (Bonadio and McDonagh, 2020, p.6). In the Chinese case *Feilin v. Baidu*, the court, recognising the economic and communicative significance of computer-generated works, held that granting specific legal entitlements to individuals better served the public interest than leaving such works in the public domain. Considering the contributions of the developer and the user, the court deemed it more appropriate to extend legal protection to the user, noting that the developer had already recovered their investment through licensing or ownership rights, whereas the user possessed both the motivation and intent to utilise and distribute the output, having initiated the process with specific keyword input.

5.2. Limits of User Authorship

For a work created with the involvement of an artificial intelligence system to qualify for copyright protection, the human user must design the prompt so precisely that almost no creative discretion remains to the system's inherently unpredictable processes. In other words, the generation process must be structured in a way that leaves minimal space for random or autonomous decisions by the AI. However, this would require highly advanced text-to-image models capable of consistently following human directions. Despite the remarkable progress in this field, current technologies may still fall short of this standard. For example, user experiences with DALL-E 2—presently among the most sophisticated systems—show that it often struggles to carry out even meticulously detailed commands (Hertzmann, 2022). Copyright protection can therefore arise only in cases where the output of an artificial intelligence system accurately and fully embodies the substance of the user's prompt. The principal limitation of employing an AI assistant lies in the fact that users cannot intervene in or oversee how the model interprets and executes the instructions provided (Ginsburg and Budiardjo, 2020, p.444). A recent decision by the U.S. Copyright Office has shed light on the question of user contribution in works generated with the assistance of artificial intelligence. The case concerned *Zarya of the Dawn*, a short comic book authored by Kris Kashtanova. Kashtanova conceived the storyline and wrote all textual components of the work, whereas the visual illustrations were produced using the AI system Midjourney. Initially, the U.S. Copyright Office granted copyright protection for the entire comic book. However, once it became apparent that the images had been created through an AI tool, this protection was partially revoked (*Zarya of the Dawn* U.S. Copyright Office, 2022, Correspondence from the U.S. Copyright Office to the lawyer, pp.1-2). Her legal counsel contended that Kashtanova

exercised creative authority by selecting and arranging the components of the artwork, a process analogous to a photographer deciding the conditions under which a photograph is captured. Furthermore, each AI-generated image had been refined through additional editing processes (Zarya of the Dawn U.S Copyright Office, 2022, pp.6-8). The attorney further contended that the illustrations should qualify for copyright protection since the AI system functioned merely as a technical instrument, similar to a camera (Zarya of the Dawn U.S Copyright Office, 2022, p. 4). The U.S. Copyright Office, however, rejected these arguments, reaffirming that copyright law extends solely to works created by human authors. Although Kashtanova had been involved in shaping the illustrations, this did not change the fact that the actual generation of the images was performed by Midjourney. As a result, Kashtanova was granted copyright solely over the textual material and the way the text and images were selected, organised, and combined, but not over the illustrations themselves (Zarya of the Dawn U.S Copyright Office, 2023, Correspondence from U.S Copyright Office to the lawyer, p.1). Thus, her contribution, though creative, did not amount to authorship in the legal sense, as contribution cannot substitute for creation.

5.3. *Summary*

This section adopts an illustrative approach to examine user authorship in AI-generated content, drawing on examples created through interaction with an AI image generator. The examples are intended to illustrate, in a practical manner, the extent of creative influence that a human user may exert when interacting with an artificial intelligence system. *Figure 1* was generated from the simple prompt, “a cat in the space.” The user’s contribution in this instance consisted solely of these five words, while the AI system, Night Cafe, autonomously determined all artistic aspects such as composition, colour palette, and style. The human involvement here is therefore minimal, providing no substantial creative input that could justify authorship. However, a more complex scenario arises when the user specifies additional elements—such as subject matter, colour scheme, or atmosphere—within the prompt. In such cases, the user arguably contributes more directly to the conceptualisation of the image and might hold certain expectations about the final output. For instance, consider the following detailed prompt: “A Bengal cat stands proudly on the surface of an alien planet, overlooking a glowing cosmic horizon filled with twin suns and drifting asteroids. The cat’s fur is short, sleek, and richly coloured in golden brown with distinct dark rosettes and stripes — every hair illuminated by the harsh sunlight of space. Its emerald-green eyes are wide and expressive, one reflecting the bright Earth below, the other glinting with a single tear suspended in zero gravity. The tear catches the light, creating a small glowing droplet that drifts gently toward the inside of the helmet. The cat’s expression is calm but filled with emotion — a mix of focus, sadness, and quiet acceptance. Its ears are slightly tilted back, and whiskers curve naturally inside the helmet. The cat wears a specially designed feline space suit, lightweight and aerodynamic, made specifically for feline anatomy with soft pressure panels and a transparent helmet shaped to fit its head comfortably. On its chest is a glowing insignia shaped like a constellation — the mark of the Galactic Feline Command. A long, elegant tail extends from the back of the suit, reinforced with energy filaments that emit faint light trails as the cat moves. Behind it, a team of robotic drones’ hovers in formation, awaiting orders. The sky is

filled with nebula clouds in rich hues of violet, indigo, and crimson. The atmosphere is cinematic and awe-inspiring — a perfect blend of science fiction and majestic authority” (Figure 2).

Figure 1

Figure 2

As this example demonstrates, even an elaborate and highly descriptive prompt does not necessarily ensure that the generated image will correspond precisely to the user’s envisioned result. The AI system independently interprets the textual input and makes its own aesthetic and compositional decisions. Generative AI inherently operates with an element of autonomy, meaning that the final output inevitably diverges, at least in part, from the user’s original conception.

Merely organising others to produce creative works, providing technical means, gathering data, or suggesting ideas does not in itself constitute authorship. The decisive criterion lies in whether a substantial degree of intellectual and creative effort has been invested in the production of the work. Accordingly, where a user intervenes in the generation process by formulating prompts, refining inputs, and selecting, modifying, or rejecting outputs, while the artificial intelligence system performs an auxiliary function, the resulting work may be attributed to the user. The fact that AI-generated outputs inevitably contain a degree of randomness—an inherent feature of machine learning systems—does not, in itself, preclude the recognition of user authorship, provided that such randomness is effectively subordinated to human intellectual control over the creative outcome. Determining whether this threshold is met inevitably raises methodological challenges. Copyright law, however, has long relied on *ex post* evaluative criteria rather than direct insight into the internal mechanics of the creative process. Courts may therefore assess authorship by reference to indirect indicators, including the extent of human decision-making throughout the generation process, the formulation and iterative refinement of prompts, the examination of successive drafts of generated outputs, the deliberate selection or rejection of particular results, and the presence of a coherent expressive vision attributable to the user. Where a user engages critically with multiple generated drafts and progressively refines the output in pursuit of a specific aesthetic or conceptual objective, such iterative engagement may evidence meaningful creative control over the final work. While AI-based analytical tools may assist in identifying technical patterns

or similarities, their role should remain auxiliary, as the ultimate determination of authorship and originality involves normative judgments concerning creativity and personal expression that must rest with human evaluators.

6. The Extent to Which Human Involvement Is Necessary for Copyright Protection. The Incompatibility of Artificial Intelligence System with Authorship

As *Annemarie Bridy* insightfully notes, the discussion on whether artificial intelligence can be treated as an author essentially involves examining the degree of human contribution required by copyright law (Bridy, 2012, pp.10-11). This raises a central question: can a computer, machine, or robot be regarded as a legitimate author? As AI systems evolve toward greater independence, identifying a human participant who bears responsibility for the creative process leading to the final product becomes increasingly complex. In these situations, one could contend that the machine itself carries out the central creative tasks—those understood within the framework of originality reflecting the author’s creative insight, technical skill, and dedicated effort (Pinto, 2019; Turner, 2019, p.122). Since the system directly executes the acts necessary for producing the work, it could be viewed as the sole agent of creation (Grubow, 2018, p.409). If machines were to be accepted as authors of copyrightable works, it would logically follow that AI and robotic systems would need to be granted legal rights. Although this hypothesis presents an intellectually engaging and imaginative possibility, it remains improbable in practice, particularly when it comes to acknowledging legal rights for AI or robots (Miller, 1993, p.1043; Ginsburg and Budiardjo, 2020, p.343; Grimmelmann, 2016, p.403). The primary and most apparent challenge is that artificial systems and autonomous technologies do not have legal personhood, and therefore are incapable of holding or exercising rights, including those conferred by copyright (Bridy, 2012, p.21; Butler, 1982, p. 740). Another significant argument against granting copyright to artificial intelligence concerns the very rationale of copyright law itself. The central objective of copyright protection has always been to encourage and reward human creativity by conferring exclusive rights on the author (Gervais, 2019, p.2079). Extending authorship to AI systems would therefore undermine this foundational principle. Unlike human creators, artificial intelligence does not act out of personal motivation, emotional investment, or the pursuit of recognition. Its operation depends solely on the data it receives and the algorithms through which it processes that information, ultimately generating an output devoid of intentional or creative aspiration (Palace, 2019, p.234).

Artificial intelligence cannot be viewed as an inherent source of creativity. Although AI systems may be designed to include stochastic elements in their computational processes, allowing them to produce outcomes that are unexpected or novel, randomness alone cannot equate to genuine creativity. Nonetheless, it is argued that “deep learning” systems—unlike clearly programmed and transparent “expert systems”—do not alter the fundamental character of AI as a human-designed and human-directed instrument. The programmer still determines what tasks the system will perform, the data it will analyse, the parameters it will follow, the goals it must optimise (its “loss function”), and the moment it begins operation. AI systems can only be regarded as sophisticated instruments operated by human creators or users. A

person may employ and control such a tool without necessarily understanding every detail of its internal functioning (Türkmenoğlu, 2023, pp.250-251). Consequently, the proposition that AI could hold the legal status of an author or owner of a work cannot be sustained.

7. Evaluating the Public Domain Approach as a Response to the Authorship Dilemma

When all other proposed solutions prove insufficient, one remaining possibility is to classify computer-generated work as part of the public domain. This approach relies on the premise that such creations lack human intellectual involvement and therefore do not meet the fundamental requirement of authorship necessary for copyright protection (Błaszczyk, 2023; Grimmelmann, 2016, p. 411; Ginsburg and Budiardja, 2019, pp.446-447; Sun, 2022, pp. 1213, 1217; Kasdan and Pattengale, 2022). Programmers already receive remuneration for their contributions through software sales and licensing arrangements. By contrast, users of generative systems are motivated not only by their payment for access to these programs but also by the expectation that their intellectual input may be recognised as authorship. If all AI-generated outputs were to be placed in the public domain, this potential acknowledgment — and the incentive it provides — would disappear entirely. Another difficulty with this solution lies in the behavioural consequences it might generate. Users could be tempted to misrepresent their own role in the creative process to claim authorship and thereby obtain copyright protection (Samuelson, 1986, pp.1225 – 1226). From a broader policy perspective, assigning AI-generated content to the public domain may also impede technological and artistic progress. The absence of proprietary incentives could discourage the development and dissemination of new works, thereby undermining the advancement of knowledge, science, and culture. Consequently, it is necessary to identify an alternative party who could justifiably be credited as the author of computer-generated works. In our view, the most fitting candidate is the owner of the AI system, and the rationale for this position will be examined in the following section.

8. Towards a Pragmatic Solution: Granting Authorship to the Owner of the AI System

The High Court of England and Wales, in the *DABUS* case (Thaler v The Comptroller-General of Patents, Designs and Trademarks, 2020, para. 35), concluded that only natural persons qualify as inventors. More importantly for this research paper, the court suggested that, in cases where inventions are generated by AI, ownership should be assigned to the person or entity that holds the AI system. Smith J explained this by reference to a general rule: the owner of an object typically owns the fruits it produces; for example, the proprietor of a fruit tree usually owns the fruit it bears (*DABUS*, para. 49(3)(a)). This decision appears to be among the first judicial recognitions that intellectual property rights in AI-generated works may vest in the owner of the AI system (Matulionyte and Lee, 2022, p.25).

An AI owner can be described as an individual or entity that has purchased and invested resources into an AI system. In assessing AI ownership, the focus is less on the intellectual contribution to the output and more on the extent of investment in the AI itself (Matulionyte and Lee, 2022, p.27). From this standpoint, those who provide the investment for the AI can be considered the rightful owners of the outputs it generates (Abbott and Rothman, 2023,

p.1198; Matulionyte and Lee, 2022, pp.27-28). Recognising the AI system's owner as the copyright holder is generally seen as the most workable solution, offering greater clarity and enforceability than assigning rights to the programmer or the end user (Abbott, 2016, pp.1113-1114). Determining copyright ownership for programmers or users requires evaluating the significance of their contribution to the AI-generated work, which must be assessed on a case-by-case basis. However, identifying who has made a substantial contribution can often be difficult (Matulionyte and Lee 2022, p.30). In situations where no party's contribution is clearly substantial, the work may default to the public domain (Ginsburg and Budiardjo, 2020, pp.447-448). Recognising the AI owner as the copyright holder avoids these complications (Matulionyte and Lee, 2022, pp.30-32). Allocating copyright to the AI owner eliminates the need to analyse the precise contributions of programmers or users. Ownership can be established based solely on possession of and investment in the AI system, irrespective of creative input. Nevertheless, if a user significantly shapes the AI-generated work, granting ownership to the AI owner could be considered unfair (Matulionyte and Lee, 2022, pp.32-35), potentially leading to disputes. In such cases, contractual arrangements between the AI owner and programmer or user provide a practical mechanism to address issues such as compensation or royalties for AI-generated outputs (Abbott, 2016, pp.1114-1117). Moreover, Nycum and Fong maintain that, because copyright operates within the realm of private law, the parties should have the flexibility to assign ownership of AI-generated content (AIGC) through contractual arrangements (Nycum and Fong, 1985 cited in: Lu, 2025, p.93). Consequently, a balanced approach to resolving the allocation of copyright in AIGC would allow the parties to determine ownership contractually where possible, while defaulting to statutory assignment of copyright to the AI owner in the absence of such agreements. Additionally, applying the AI owner rule can reduce the likelihood of co-ownership disputes or make them less problematic. Granting copyright in AI-generated outputs to all individuals involved in producing the final work could give rise to situations where both the AI developer and the user have contributed enough to be considered joint owners (Ginsburg and Budiardjo, 2020, p.440). In such circumstances, managing and enforcing rights can become both burdensome and expensive, particularly when the parties have no prior commercial ties. The costs and complications of joint ownership may undermine the work's overall value and limit its use, preventing it from achieving the level of societal benefit it otherwise could (Lee, 2016, pp.124-130). For example, if a visual artist employs the generative AI system *Midjourney* to create a digital artwork, and both *Midjourney*'s developer and the artist are recognised as co-owners of the resulting image, exercising rights over that work would become cumbersome. The artist would need the developer's consent to reproduce, license, or sell the image, and the same requirement would apply to the developer, significantly complicating the commercial use of the artwork. Granting ownership to the AI owner, however, minimises the risk of such co-ownership conflicts.

Attributing full authorship to the owner of an artificial intelligence system in all circumstances risks undermining the foundational principles of copyright law, which are traditionally anchored in the concept of personal intellectual creation. Although the economic investment, organisational responsibility, and risk assumed by the AI owner warrant legal consideration, these factors alone are insufficient to justify the recognition of authorship in the

absence of a genuine creative contribution. In such situations, the automatic elevation of ownership or investment to the level of authorship appears conceptually unsound. Therefore, we contend that AI-generated outputs cannot be subjected to a uniform legal classification. Where the user's involvement in the generation process is substantial, intentional, and perceptibly reflected in the final output, authorship should be attributed to the user as the bearer of creative expression. By contrast, where human input remains limited and the output is shaped predominantly by the autonomous functioning of the artificial intelligence system, the attribution of full copyright protection to the AI owner would conflict with the human-centred structure of copyright law. In such cases, a limited form of sui generis or neighbouring-rights protection—grounded in investment, organisation, and technical control rather than creativity—offers a more coherent and balanced solution. This differentiated approach preserves the integrity of authorship while ensuring that economically valuable AI-generated outputs are not left entirely without legal protection.

9. Conclusion

The growing integration of artificial intelligence into artistic production challenges the traditional foundations of copyright law, particularly the human-centred conception of authorship. As generative systems become increasingly capable of producing outputs that are indistinguishable from human-made works in both form and commercial value, the question is no longer whether AI-assisted creations should be addressed by copyright law, but how such protection can be reconciled with its core principles. This study has demonstrated that artificial intelligence, notwithstanding its technical sophistication, cannot be regarded as an author in the legal sense. Current AI systems lack consciousness, intentionality, and self-expression—elements that remain central to the concept of authorship across both civil law and common law traditions. Randomness, autonomy in execution, or algorithmic complexity cannot substitute for creative intention. Consequently, the attribution of authorship to AI systems themselves must be rejected.

The analysis further shows that neither developers nor owners of AI systems can automatically be recognised as authors of AI-generated works. While developers may legitimately claim authorship over the software they design, the necessary personal and intellectual connection between the developer and the individual output is typically absent. Similarly, allocating authorship to the owner of an AI system solely on the basis of investment or control risks detaching copyright protection from creative contribution. In such situations, the automatic elevation of ownership or financial risk to the level of authorship would conflict with the fundamental logic of copyright law. At the same time, we confirm that users of AI systems may, in certain circumstances, satisfy the originality threshold required for authorship. Where a user meaningfully shapes the creative outcome—through the formulation of detailed prompts, iterative refinement, selection or rejection of outputs, and post-processing decisions—the resulting work may bear the user's personal imprint. However, user involvement varies significantly in practice, and not every interaction with an AI system

reflects a level of creative control sufficient to justify authorship. This variability renders a uniform attribution model unsuitable.

Against this background, we are arguing for a more differentiated legal approach. Where a work reflects substantial human creative control, authorship should be attributed to the relevant human contributor, typically the user. By contrast, where human involvement remains organisational, technical, or merely facilitative—without shaping the expressive content of the output—authorship attribution is not justified. In such cases, protecting the AI owner through neighbouring rights or a limited *sui generis* regime may offer a more coherent solution. This approach acknowledges economic investment and risk-taking without diluting the concept of authorship itself. More broadly, the findings of this research underscore the need for a refined understanding of creativity in the age of human–AI collaboration. Human creativity does not disappear when computational tools are employed; rather, it manifests in new forms, including system configuration, dataset curation, prompt engineering, and evaluative judgment. Where these elements decisively shape the expressive outcome, they merit legal recognition.

Accordingly, we are supporting the development of a differentiated category for computer-generated works involving significant human input, accompanied by procedural mechanisms that enhance transparency. The disclosure of AI use and the possibility of substantiating human contribution through prompts, drafts, or revision histories would allow courts and copyright offices to assess originality on an *ex post* basis, consistent with existing copyright methodology. Ultimately, copyright law should move beyond the formal question of who or what technically produced a work and instead focus on who exercised creative control and intentional direction over the final output. Such a shift preserves the human-centred foundations of copyright law while allowing it to adapt to contemporary creative practices shaped by artificial intelligence.

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